

The Reactivity of the Methylene Group in Coumarin-4-acetic Acids and their Esters.

Condensation with Salicylaldehyde to 4:3-Dicoumaryls.

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Sometime ago it was observed by one of us that the ethyl ester of 7-methyl-coumarin-4-acetic acid (Fries and Volk, *Annalen*, 1911, 379, 107) readily formed a yellow monosodium derivative when treated with metallic sodium (wire) in dry solvents like ether or benzene in the cold. It was quickly hydrolysed by cold water regenerating the original ester and behaved in other respects like the sodium derivatives of phenylacetic and cyanacetic esters, showing clearly that it was formed by the replacement of one of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group by metallic sodium. This observation which was repeated in the cases of other coumarin- and naphthapyrone-acetic esters made it obviously desirable to study the reactivity of the methylene group in these bodies as a class and to compare them with the phenylacetic esters to which they bear a close resemblance in structure. In the present communication we have studied only one particular example of this reactivity, *viz.*, their property of condensing with salicylaldehyde. The reaction between phenylacetic acid or its ethyl ester and salicylaldehyde has been the subject of several investigations (Oglialozo,

Gazetta, 1879, 9, 428; Frank and Kostanecki, Ber., 1905, 38, 939, etc.). A few preliminary experiments relating to the determination of the most favourable conditions under which this reaction took place led to results which are not perhaps without significance in their bearing on the relative influence of the benzene and the pyrone rings upon the reactivity of the $\text{CH}_2\text{-COOH}$ group attached to them. It was found that in the case of phenylacetic acid the best results were uniformly obtained by working under the conditions of Perkin's reaction, *i.e.*, by heating the free acid and the aldehyde with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, whilst if the ethyl ester of the acid be employed and the experiment carried out under the conditions of Knoevenagel's reaction, no condensation took place at the ordinary temperature and it was only after continuous boiling for 10 to 12 hours that a very small amount of the 3-phenyl-coumarin could be isolated. The coumarin-acetic acids, on the other hand, were found to condense almost quantitatively when an alcoholic solution of their ethyl esters was warmed for a short time with the aldehyde in the presence of a few drops of piperidine (Knoevenagel); the free acids also reacted either by Perkin or Knoevenagel's methods, although the yields of the product were somewhat poorer. These experiments, therefore, would lead one to the conclusion that the reactivity of the methylene group in coumarin-acetic esters is greater than that of this group in phenylacetic esters at least so far as their power of condensing with salicylaldehyde is concerned, although in the case of the free acids, the difference, if any, is hardly appreciable.

In the course of this work an unexpected irregularity was found to present itself in connection with the condensation of substances in which either of the reactants contained more than one hydroxyl group in their molecules. Thus, whilst 7-hydroxy-coumarin-4-acetic ester reacted

smoothly with salicylaldehyde in the presence of piperidine, the 7:8-dihydroxy-coumarinacetic ester failed to give any condensation product at all under the same conditions. Similarly, resorcylic aldehyde could not be made to undergo condensation with any of the coumarin-acetic esters by Knoevenagel's reaction. It should be mentioned, however, that in both these cases condensation was brought about without much difficulty under the conditions of Perkin's reaction.

The compounds described in this paper have been termed 4:3'-dicoumaryls, the condensation of salicylaldehyde with the coumarinacetic esters taking place in the following manner:

The only compound of a similar type to which reference is found in literature is a 3:3'-dicoumaryl prepared by heating salicylaldehyde with sodium succinate and acetic anhydride in a sealed tube at 140° for forty hours (Dyson, *Trans.* 1887, 51, 62; also Fittig, *Annalen*, 1889, 255, 1).

This dicoumaryl is described by Dyson as a light yellow crystalline powder insoluble in the ordinary organic solvents, and not fusing when heated up to 330°C; these properties are shared to a large extent by the

4: 3'-dicoumaryls which are usually coloured, have high melting points, and dissolve very sparingly in alcohol, acetic acid, benzene, etc., the most convenient medium for their crystallisation being nitrobenzene diluted with acetic acid or alcohol. Boiling alkalis dissolve them only slowly, acids precipitating the unchanged dicoumaryls; if however, the acidification be carried out at a low temperature, unstable acids are first precipitated in the manner of the coumarinic acids which dissolve completely in cold sodium carbonate but lose their property on standing for some time being changed into the original substances. They could not be made to combine with sodium bisulphite, a result which is in accord with the observation previously made (Dey and Row, *Trans.*, 1924, 125, 554) that the presence of an alkyl group—the coumaryl group in the present instance—in either the 3- or the 4-position hinders the formation of additive compounds.

The bromination of these dicoumaryls has also been studied in one case. The introduction of the halogen can be carried out under the usual conditions, although it is found difficult to restrict its entrance into only one position in the molecule. Thus, on treating 7-methyl-4: 3'-dicoumaryl with an amount of bromine calculated for the introduction of only one atom of the halogen, the product that was obtained, was found to be largely a mixture of a dibromo-derivative, a probable mono-bromo-derivative which could not be purified, and some unchanged material. The dibromo-compound could be readily prepared by boiling in glacial acetic acid with a slight excess over the required proportions of bromine. One of the bromine atoms was proved to have occupied the 3-position that remained free in the molecule, as it was split off on boiling with alcoholic potash with the formation of a 3'-coumaryl-3-benzfuran-2-carboxylic acid

acid. After several trials, the following conditions were found to be the most suitable for ensuring a satisfactory yield by this reaction :

Citric acid (24 grams) and concentrated sulphuric acid (32 c.c.) were mixed in a capacious flask and shaken for half an hour, and the mixture then slowly warmed on a large water bath to a temperature of 70°C, the thermometer dipping in the mixture. Carbon monoxide was copiously given off and the mixture left at this temperature for 10 to 15 minutes. As soon as the evolution of gas slackened, the flask was removed from the bath, allowed to stand for about 5 minutes till the liquid became clear and free from gas bubbles, and then cooled in ice. The phenol or naphthol (1/10 mol.), and a further amount of strong sulphuric acid (14 c.c.) were now gradually added, and the mixture shaken, taking care not to allow the temperature to rise above 10°. The dark-coloured semi-solid mass was left in the ice chamber overnight, and then poured into excess of cold water when usually a bulky precipitate of a yellow to brown colour separated out. The precipitate was digested with N/10 sodium carbonate solution (about a litre) for 10 minutes on a boiling water bath, allowed to settle and filtered. On acidifying the filtrate, the coumarinacetic acid came down as an amorphous precipitate which was purified by one or two crystallisations from alcohol or acetic acid. The yield varied in the cases of different phenols and naphthols, that in the case of α -naphthol amounting to 60 per cent. of what is required by theory. The residue insoluble in sodium carbonate was found to consist of the corresponding 4-methyl-coumarin in an almost pure condition, being evidently derived from the partial decomposition of the acetone dicarboxylic acid in the course of the process into aceto-acetic acid and carbon dioxide.

A. DI-COUMARYLS.

I. COMPOUNDS OBTAINED FROM α -NAPHTHAPYRONE-4-ACETIC ACID AND ITS ETHYL ESTER.*3'-Coumaryl-4- α -naphthapyrone.*

Preparation by Perkin's reaction :

Dry sodium- α -naphthapyrone-4-acetate (from 4 grams of the acid), salicylaldehyde (3.3 grams), and acetic anhydride (12 grams) were mixed in a flask and heated on a sand-bath to 150° under reflux for 6 to 7 hours. The product was thrown into water, boiled to decompose the excess of acetic anhydride, and the precipitate digested for a few minutes with sodium carbonate solution. The filtrate gave, on acidification, a small quantity of a brown solid which was found to be too impure and was not investigated further. The dark coloured residue was washed with small amounts of hot glacial acetic acid in order to remove tarry matters and other impurities, dried in the air, and crystallised by dissolving in hot nitrobenzene and diluting with alcohol. Shinning pale yellow needles came down which melted at 255°C (uncorr.), the pure crystals weighing more than 2.5 grams. (Found: C=77.30, H=3.69. $C_{22}H_{12}O_4$, requires C=77.64, H=3.53 per cent.)

Preparation by Knoevenagel's reaction :

Salicylaldehyde (3 grams), α -naphthapyrone-4-ethyl acetate (5.6 grams), and absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) were mixed together and treated with 5 to 6 drops of piperidine, the mixture turning a deep yellow colour. It was heated to boiling on a water-bath under a reflux condenser when the clear yellow solution slowly became turbid and in less than half an hour fine yellow crystals began to separate out. At the end of about two hours the contents of the flask had very nearly solidified, when

the precipitate was filtered off, and the filtrate heated again in the water-bath for another 2 to 3 hours, a further crop of crystals being thus obtained. The crystals, after washing with hot alcohol, were found to be quite pure (m. p. 255°), the total yield being nearly 6 grams, corresponding to 80 per cent. of that theoretically obtainable.

3'-coumaryl-4-*a*-naphthapyrone crystallises in small needles of a pale yellow colour which are practically insoluble in alcohol, ether, benzene, etc., dissolves sparingly in boiling glacial acetic acid and more readily in nitrobenzene. Cold alkalis have no action on the substance, but on boiling with 25 per cent. caustic soda, it slowly goes into solution from which acids precipitate the unchanged substance. If, however, the alkaline solution be faintly acidified at a low temperature (0° to 5°C), a coumarinic acid gradually settles down. The latter is completely soluble in dilute sodium carbonate, but on allowing to stand at the ordinary temperature for some time or in boiling with water, it quickly loses this property and becomes insoluble in cold alkalis showing that reversion to coumarin had taken place. All attempts to convert the dicoumaryl into the stable coumaric acid either by boiling with concentrated alkali or with bisulphite and alkali were unsuccessful.

*6'-Bromo-3'-coumaryl-4-*a*-naphthapyrone.*

This was prepared by boiling an alcoholic solution of *a*-naphthapyrone-4-ethylacetate (3 grams) and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (2.5 gram) with a few drops of piperidine in the manner described in the preceding case. Crystallisation from nitrobenzene and acetic acid gave more than 3 grams of yellow needles melting at 292°C (uncorr.) (Found: Br=19.85. C₂₃H₁₁O₄Br requires Br=19.09 per cent.)

6'-Chloro-3'-coumaryl-4-a-naphthapyrone.

This was obtained from 5-chloro-salicylaldehyde and α -naphthapyrone-4-ethylacetate by Knoevenagel's reaction in a yield of nearly 80 per cent. of that required by theory. It crystallised from nitrobenzene and alcohol in pale yellow needles melting at 276°-277°. (Found: Cl=9·54. $C_{22}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires Cl=9·48 per cent.)

6':8'-Dichloro-3'-coumaryl-4-a-naphthapyrone, prepared from 3:5-dichloro-salicylaldehyde, crystallised in magnificent golden yellow needles, melting at 301°C. (Found Cl=17·34. $C_{22}H_{10}O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl=17·36 per cent.)

6'-Nitro-3'-coumaryl-4-a-naphthapyrone, prepared from 5-nitro-salicylaldehyde, crystallised in deep yellow needles darkening at 310°C and gradually decomposing above this temperature. The substance dissolves readily in warm dilute caustic soda, with a deep red colour from which, on acidifying in the cold, a fairly stable coumarinic acid can be isolated. (Found: C=68·63, H=2·96. $C_{22}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C=68·57, H=2·85 per cent.)

7'-Acetoxy-3'-coumaryl-4-a-naphthapyrone.

Resorcylic aldehyde (2·75 grams), sodium α -naphthapyrone-1-acetate (5·5 grams), and acetic anhydride (10 grams) were heated together for 6 hours at 160°-170°C, and the resulting product poured into excess of water. The dark brown precipitate was washed with hot water, digested for sometime with 10 per cent. caustic soda, and the residual yellowish brown powder crystallised twice from hot nitrobenzene with the addition of alcohol. Deep yellow prismatic needles were deposited darkening at 270° and melting at 282°-284°C. (Found: C=72·81, H=3·78. $C_{21}H_{14}O_4$ requires C=72·36, H=3·52 per cent.)

Attempts to hydrolyse the substance always resulted in the production of a dark pasty mass which could not be purified.

3'-β-Naphthacoumaryl-4-α-naphthapyrone.

. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (2 grams) α-naphthapyrone-4-ethylacetate (3 grams) and absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) were boiled with a few drops of piperidine under a reflux condenser for 3-4 hours. The precipitated solid was washed with boiling alcohol and then crystallised from nitrobenzene which gave small fibrous crystals of a pale yellow colour which did not melt or darken even at 310° C. An interesting point to be noted about this compound is its colour which is much lighter in shade than that of most of the other coumaryl-α-naphthapyrones, although its molecular complexity is much greater. (Found: C=79·8, H=3·7. $C_{26}H_{14}O_4$ requires C=80·0, H=3·59 per cent.)

II. DICOUMARYLS FROM β-NAPHTHAPYRONE-4-ETHYL ACETATE.

3'-Coumaryl-4-β-naphthapyrone.

4 grams of the ester, 2 grams of salicylaldehyde, and 6 drops of piperidine were boiled with 50 c.c. alcohol for about 12 hours. The reaction occurred much less readily than in the case of the α-naphthapyrone ethylacetate, and the precipitated solid had to be repeatedly filtered off and the filtrate re-heated before a satisfactory yield could be obtained. Light yellow needles were obtained after one crystallisation from nitrobenzene and alcohol, melting at 282° C (uncorr.). The yield amounted to 1·6 grams. (Found: C=77·18, H=3·46. $C_{22}H_{12}O_4$ requires C=77·64, H=3·53 per cent.)

6'-Chloro-3'-coumaryl-4-β-naphthapyrone, from 5-chloro-salicylaldehyde and β-naphthapyrone ethylacetate, crystallised from a large excess of glacial acetic acid in hard prismatic needles of a very pale yellow colour which darkened at 270°, and melted at 276°—278°. (Found: Cl=8.97. $C_{22}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires Cl=9.48 per cent.)

6'-Bromo-3'-coumaryl-4-β-naphthapyrone.

This was prepared in the usual way from 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde (4 grams), and the pyrone ester (6 grams), by boiling in alcoholic solution in the presence of piperidine for several hours. It was deposited from acetic acid in short yellow prismatic needles melting at 260°. (Found: Br=19.21. $C_{22}H_{11}O_4Br$ requires Br=19.09 per cent.)

III. DICOUMARYLS FROM 7-METHYL-COUMARIN-4-ACETIC ESTER.

7-Methyl-4:3'-dicoumaryl.

This was prepared both by Perkin's reaction from salicylaldehyde, sodium-7-methyl-coumarin-4-acetate and acetic anhydride, and by Knoevenagel's reaction from the ester (5 grams) and aldehyde (3 grams) and a little piperidine. The latter process gave the better yield amounting to a little over 70 per cent. of that obtainable by theory. It crystallised from acetic acid in soft colourless wooly needles melting at 247° C. (Found: C=75.14, H=4.12. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C=75.00, H=3.95 per cent.)

7-Methyl-6'-bromo-4:3'-dicoumaryl.

It was prepared by the condensation of 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde (4 grams) with 7-methyl-coumarin ethyl

acetate (5 grams) in the presence of piperidine in the usual way. Crystallisation from nitrobenzene diluted with acetic acid yielded colourless ferny needles melting at 292°. (Found: Br = 20.59. $C_{15}H_{11}O_4Br$ requires Br = 20.88 per cent.)

7-Methyl-6'-chloro-4:3'-dicoumaryl, from the corresponding chloro-salicylaldehyde, crystallised from acetic acid in colourless silky needles melting at 288°C. (Found: Cl = 10.23. $C_{15}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires Cl = 10.49 per cent.)

7-Methyl-6':8'-dichloro-4:3'-dicoumaryl, prepared from 3:5-dichloro-salicylaldehyde, crystallised in pale yellow needles melting at 286°C. (Found: Cl = 19.41. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl = 19.04 per cent.)

Action of Alkalis on 7-Methyl-4:3'-dicoumaryl.

The substance dissolves with great difficulty in alkalis, more than two hours, boiling with excess of 10 per cent. caustic soda being found necessary to get it into solution. A neutral solution to litmus or phenolphthalein of the sodium salt of the coumarinic acid could not be prepared by the usual methods, the sodium coumarinate in aqueous solutions being alkaline to test papers. Dilute nitric acid was, therefore, cautiously added in the cold till there was just a trace of a permanent precipitate. This was filtered off and the pale yellow silver salt was precipitated from the filtrate by adding a slight excess of silver nitrate. The salt after drying on a porous plate in the vacuum, was analysed. (Found: Ag = 41.48. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5Ag_2$ requires Ag = 40.37 per cent.)

The analysis seems to show that the acid is formed by the opening up of only *one* of the pyrone rings, this being presumably derived from the coumarin ring in which the 3 position is free, as substitution in the latter position has been observed to have a great hindering effect on the opening of the pyrone nucleus.

3: (1')-Dibromo-7-methyl-4:3'-dicoumaryl.

The dicoumaryl (3 gms.), bromine (2 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) were boiled together under a reflux condenser with the addition of a trace of iodine, until the colour of the bromine vapour had practically disappeared. The dibromo-derivative which was almost insoluble in acetic acid was collected, washed with hot acetic acid, and crystallised twice from nitrobenzene. It formed colourless hexagonal plates melting at 280°-82° C. (Found: Br=34.92. $C_{19}H_{10}O_4Br_2$ requires Br=34.63 per cent.)

6'-Methyl-(1')-bromo-3-(3'-coumaryl)-benzofuran-2-carboxylic Acid.

The above dibromo-compound (1.5 gms.) was finely powdered and boiled for about an hour with a 40 per cent. solution of caustic soda (6 grams) and alcohol (10 c.c.), when the sodium salt of the above acid separated out as a shining crystalline mass. This was collected, dissolved in water and the solution acidified when a bulky white gelatinous precipitate came down, which became granular and easy to filter on boiling. It was completely soluble in cold sodium carbonate, and dissolved in strong sulphuric acid with a yellow colour which, on warming, turned deep red in the manner of the coumarones. Crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave colourless thin needles melting at 260° C with evolution of gas. (Found: Br=19.67. $C_{18}H_{11}O_5Br$ requires Br=20.05 per cent.)

IV. DICOUMARYLS FROM 7-HYDROXY-COUMARIN-4-ACETIC ACID.*7-Hydroxy-4:3'-dicoumaryl*

This was obtained in an excellent yield by the condensation of 7-hydroxy-coumarin ethyl-acetate and

salicylaldehyde in the presence of piperidine. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in small colourless needles darkening at 300°, and melting at 311°C. A noteworthy feature of this compound is its property of dissolving in dilute alkalis with a yellow colour without the least fluorescence, although both 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin and 7-hydroxy-coumarin-4-acetic acid are strongly fluorescent in alkaline solutions. (Found: C=71.01, H=3.45. $C_{13}H_{10}O_5$ requires C=70.58, H=3.27 per cent.)

Its *acetyl* derivative, prepared by the action on it of acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, crystallises from acetic acid in colourless woolly needles and melts at 253°C.

Its *benzoyl* derivative formed by benzoylating in pyridine solution was obtained in colourless needles melting at 234°C.

7-Methoxy-4:3'-dicoumaryl was prepared synthetically from the 7-methoxy-coumarin ethylacetate. It formed small prismatic needles melting at 241°C. (Found: C=71.00, H=3.41. $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C=71.25, H=3.75 per cent.)

7-Hydroxy-6'-bromo-4:3'-dicoumaryl.

This was obtained in a good yield from 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde and 7-hydroxy-coumarin ethylacetate by Knoevenagel's reaction. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in short colourless needles, melting at 308°-310° C with decomposition. (Found: Br=20.56. $C_{18}H_9O_5Br$ requires Br=20.78 per cent.)

7-Acetoxy-6'-bromo-4:3'-dicoumaryl crystallises in the form of long woolly needles melting at 247°-48° C. (Found: Br=19.04. $C_{20}H_{11}O_6Br$ requires Br=18.73 per cent.)

B. 3-PHENYL-COUMARINS.

6-Chloro-3-phenyl-coumarin.

Dry sodium phenyl acetate (3 grams) 5-chloro-salicylaldehyde (3.5 grams) and acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) were heated to $150^{\circ}\text{--}60^{\circ}$ for 5 hours on the sand-bath, the mixture poured into cold water, and the product worked up in the usual manner. The residue insoluble in sodium carbonate crystallised from 50 per cent. acetic acid in colourless sharp needles melting at 200°C . The sodium carbonate extract on acidification, deposited a small amount of a white precipitate which was an acid, and after crystallisation from alcohol, melted at 190°C . It was presumably the acetoxy-phenyl-coumaric acid, but was not investigated further. (Found: $\text{Cl}=13.82$. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ requires $\text{Cl}=13.84$ per cent.)

An extraordinarily poor yield of the above compound was obtained by the condensation of the chloro-salicylaldehyde and phenyl-acetic ethyl ester in the presence of piperidine, even after boiling for 8 hours.

6-Bromo-3-phenyl-coumarin was prepared in the same way by Perkin's reaction from 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde and sodium phenylacetate. It formed beautiful silky needles melting at 193°C . (Found: $\text{Br}=26.34$. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{Br}$ requires $\text{Br}=26.58$ per cent.) Only a trace of this product was obtained by carrying out the condensation by Knoevenagel's process.

6:8-dichloro-3-phenyl-coumarin, from 3:5-dichloro-salicylaldehyde and sodium phenylacetate, crystallised from acetic acid in short glistening prisms melting at 195.5°C . (Found: $\text{Cl}=23.99$. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$ requires $\text{Cl}=24.40$ per cent.)

7-Acetoxy-3-phenyl-coumarin was prepared by heating resorcylic aldehyde (4 grams), sodium phenylacetate

(5 grams) and acetic anhydride (12 grams) in an oil bath to 160° - 70° for several hours. It formed colourless crystals insoluble in cold alkalis and melted at 186°C . (Found: C = 72.66, H = 4.10. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C = 72.85, H = 4.28 per cent.)

7-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-coumarin was prepared by hydrolysing the acetyl derivative with 20 per cent. caustic potash. Crystallisation from alcohol gave fine clusters of tetragonal prisms melting at 209° - 10°C . The alcoholic solution of the substance shows a magnificent purple fluorescence, whilst the alkaline solution exhibits a fine blue fluorescence as in the case of the umbelliferous. (Found: C = 75.32, H = 4.05. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C = 75.63 H = 4.20 per cent.)

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